

**AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF DR.B.R.AMBEDKAR'S
CONTRIBUTION TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT OF INDIAN
ECONOMY**

Synoptic note of Research work

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Research Guide

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Relevance of Economic Thoughts of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar in India

Introduction:

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar is one of the a great thinker, leader and intellectual of its time in India who has not only changed the life of millions of untouchables, but shaped India as a biggest democratic nation by writing its constitution. Many of us know Bharat Ratna Dr. B. R. Ambedkar as a social reformer and a person who had fought for untouchables in India. But very few would have know that Babasaheb was a great scholar who made outstanding contributions as an economist, sociologist, legal luminary, educationalist, journalist, parliamentarian along with social reformer and human rights, Dr. Ambedka, one of the multidimensional personalities having great noteworthy contribution on economics. He led for downtrodden in the country and they were way ahead of his times. Ambedkar thoughts of economics have made a significant impact on the social movement. Dr. B. R. Ambedkar's outstanding contribution in economics and also to consider its relevance to current Indian Economy.

His teachers include the best minds of that time like John Dewey, James Shot well, Edwin Seligman, and James Harvey Robinson. His works on Economics and specifically on Indian Economy are greatly insightful and relevant even today. His dissertations and works related to Economics are: The Problem of Rupee: Its origin and its solution, The Present Problem in Indian currency, Statement of Evidence to the Royal Commission on Indian Currency and Finance, 1924-25, Ancient Indian Commerce, The Evolution of Provincial Finance in British India: A Study in the Provincial Decentralization of imperial finance, Administration and Finance of the East India Company, Small Holdings in India and their remedies. Most of the writings and speeches of Dr. B R Ambedkar are published in several volumes by department of education, Govt. of Maharashtra.

Dr.B. R. Ambedkar, affectionately known as Babasaheb, was one of the most illustrious sons of India. Dr. Ambedkar is his fights against Caste system in India, but what is not known is how Dr. Ambedkar had also impacted the Indian history and economy.he studied through the Economic, Social and Political problems facing British-India and provided bold solution to them, which are relevant even today.

Thoughts of Dr.B. R. Ambedkar for Indian Economy:

The Directive Principles of State Policy are guidelines to the central and state governments of India, to be kept in mind while framing laws and policies. These provisions, contained in Part of the Constitution of India, Welfare schemes for the weaker sections are being implemented both by the Central and state governments. To evaluate various social and economic provisions including Indian constitution and to explain their relationship with Dr. Ambedkar's ideas with a special reference to the ideas of Dr. Ambedkar. The researcher has studied the various books and articles written by Dr. Ambedkar and to highlight his economic thoughts and ideas which have a continuity and evolution. Further, she has developed a new outlook regarding Dr. B R Ambedkar's social and economic thoughts relevant in context of present scenario.

Dr Ambedkar's Economic Ideas Reflected in the Constitution is the backbone of this part. The present research problem is very much relevant in the age of globalization on which the schedule castes, scheduled tribes are suffering great deal. They can be strengthened by understanding Dt. Ambedkar progressive economic ideas, Granville Austin, a constitutional expert has pointed out in the book Indian Constitution: 'cornerstone of the nation' Dr.Ambedkar represented problem of physical and economical exploitation of rural poor through his movements. His struggle against the prevailing land tenure system called was best example of his thoughts of equilibrium. Indian economy is mixed economy and has impact of social, political and economical changes before and after independence.

Dr. Ambedkar has given new socio and political view to Indian economics. Dr. Ambedkar decided to "changeover from economics to law and politics" as he remarked in the preface of the Indian edition of the problem of the Rupee in 1947.

The main point he makes is that an alien government cannot be expected to use the funds it has to the betterment of the people. As he made it clear. "if the Executive in India did not do certain things most conducive to progress it was because by reason of its being impersonal and also by reason of its character, motives and interest it could not sympathies with the living forces operating in the Indian Society, was not charged with its wants, its pains, its cravings and its desires, was inimical to its aspirations, did not advance education. Disfavored Swedish or snapped at ant thing that smacked of nationalism.

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's some important Economic Thoughts

➤ His ideas in the field of monetary economics and Public Finance

Dr. B. R. Ambedkar meticulously analyzed the evolution of currency in India using historical perspective even during the most neglected period of Indian currency extending from 1800 to 1893, analyzed the problems related to Indian currency in the first quarter of twentieth century, and even offered solutions to deal with the instability of rupee and concerned inflation in India. In his he analyzed how rupee evolved from a double standard to a silver standard and how the evils of instability concerned with it led to its evolution towards a gold standard and again in to gold exchange standard. He also analyzed the merits and the demerits of the pure gold standard the gold exchange standard. In this regard, Ambedkar preferred the gold standard over gold exchange standard and criticized Prof. Keynes who was in favour of the gold exchange standard. In fact, Ambedkar was in favour of the gold standard of modified form. In pure gold standard, gold in some form, especially coins is used as a medium of exchange. In its modified form, paper money is also issued in addition to gold coins, and is pledged to be redeemable in gold. In contrast to this, under the gold exchange standard only paper money which can be exchanged at fixed rate with gold, is used as a medium of exchange. Here authorities back it up with foreign currency reserves of such countries which are on the gold standards. According to him, gold standard is more stable than gold exchange standard as in the former due to its intrinsic characteristics; money supply is more stable compared to the later.

➤ His ideas related to the strategy for Economic Development

Dr. Ambedkar visualizes a larger role of state and the constitutional methods to bring about inclusive economic growth and development in India. He was a champion of democracy and human rights so was against dictatorship in any form or shape. He disliked violent methods of change and believed that constitutional provisions and democratic means should be relied upon for the desired reformation. In this way, we could derive that though he believes in the greatest good of largest number of people, he disapproves violent methods and transitional dictatorship as accepted in Marxism. So here we can see his great concern for humanism as well as for individual liberty. In his memorandum submitted to the British Government titled "States and Minorities" in 1947, Dr. Ambedkar laid down a strategy for India's economic development. The strategy placed

“an obligation on the State to plan the economic life of the people on lines which would lead to highest point of productivity without closing every avenue to private enterprise and also provide for the equitable distribution of wealth”. Ambedkar believed in a classless society but not in a stateless society. He maintained that the state would continue to exist as long as human society survived.

To suggest the strategy of economic growth and development, Ambedkar analyses the problem of small land holdings in India. He found in his study that more than consolidation and enlargement of land holdings, conversion of them into economic holdings through the use of right proportions of capital and other inputs is required. Moreover, he stated that the progress of industrialization would on the one hand lessen the burden over agricultural sector by shifting the surplus labor from the land and on the other hand, manufacture more capital tools for use in agriculture sector thereby leading its progress. So his strategy for economic growth and development is an inclusive as well as right growth strategy as per best notions of Economics, whereby economic development starts with the growth of primary sector, surplus labor from it moves to secondary sector employment and simultaneous development of two sectors to reinforce each other. And on the base of proper growth of these two sectors, the tertiary sector grows. He is in favor of ‘state socialism of his own kind’; thereby state should take the responsibility of inclusive economic development.

RELEVANCE OF DR. B.R.AMBEDKAR’S ECONOMIC IDEAS:

The Directive Principles of State Policy are guidelines to the central and state governments of India, to be kept in mind while framing laws and policies. These provisions, contained in Part of the Constitution of India, Welfare schemes for the weaker sections are being implemented both by the Central and state governments. To evaluate various social and economic provisions including Indian constitution and to explain their relationship with Dr. Ambedkar’s ideas with a special reference to the ideas of Dr. Ambedkar. The researcher has studied the various books and articles written by Dr. Ambedkar and to highlight his economic thoughts and ideas which have a continuity and evolution. Further, she has developed a new outlook regarding Dr. B R Ambedkar’s social and economic thoughts relevant in context of present scenario.

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Dr. Ambedkar's economic ideas have been studied systematically. For this purpose, the constituent assembly debates have been carefully studied to evaluate the present problem. Intervening in a discussion in the Bombay Legislative Council on October 10, 1927, Dr. Ambedkar argued that the solution to the agrarian question "lies not in increasing the size of farms, but in having intensive cultivation that is employing more capital and more labour on the farms such as we have." (These and all subsequent quotations are taken from the collection of Dr. Ambedkar's writings, published by the Government of Maharashtra in 1979). Further on, he says: "The better method is to introduce cooperative agriculture and to compel owners of small strips to join in cultivation." During the process of framing the Constitution of the Republic of India, Dr. Ambedkar proposed to include certain provisions on fundamental rights, specifically a clause to the effect that the state shall provide protection against economic exploitation. Among other things, this clause proposed that: Key industries shall be owned and run by the state, Basic but non-key industries shall be owned by the state and run by the state or by corporations established by it, Agriculture shall be a state industry, and be organized by the state taking over all land and letting it out for cultivation in suitable standard sizes to residents of villages; these shall be cultivated as collective farms by groups of families.

As part of his proposals, Dr. Ambedkar provided detailed explanatory notes on the measures to protect the citizen against economic exploitation. He stated: "The main purpose behind the clause is to put an obligation on the state to plan the economic life of the people on lines which would lead to highest point of productivity without closing every avenue to private enterprise, and also provide for the equitable distribution of wealth. The plan set out in the clause proposes state ownership in agriculture with a collectivized method of cultivation and a modified form of state socialism in the field of industry.

Places squarely on the shoulders of the state the obligation to supply the capital necessary for agriculture as well as for industry." Dr. Ambedkar recognizes the importance of insurance in providing the state with "the resources necessary for financing its economic planning, in the absence of which it would have to resort to borrowing from the money market at high rates of interest" and proposes the nationalization of insurance. He categorically stated: "State socialism is essential for the rapid industrialization of India. Private enterprise cannot do it and if it did, it would produce those inequalities of wealth which private capitalism has produced in Europe and which should be a warning to Indians.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

A number of studies have been carried out covering various aspects on: Relevance of Dr. Ambedkar economic philosophy". In this study a sincere attempt has been made to carry out a review of literature concerning the present research topic. A careful analysis of relevant literature concerning the present research topic. All such details have been gathered from different sources.

1. **C. D. Naik (2008)** had written and compiled *Social and political Thought of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar* and discussed about an attempt is made to make aware of the contemporary situation vis - a vis Ambedkar's solutions, which are still having bearing on current socio-economic issues.
2. **Iswita Aditya Ray & Sarabpriyaray (2011)** the present analysis is concerned Ambedkar's philosophy regarding land reform and its relevance in present day scenario. Dr. Ambedkar stresses the need for thorough land reform, nothing that smallness or largeness of an of agriculture holding is not determined by its physical extent alone but by the intensity of cultivation as reselected in the a amount of productive investment made on the land and the amount of all other input used including labour. He also stresses the need for industrialization so as to move surplus labor from agriculture to other productive occupation accompanied by large capital investment in agriculture to raise yields.
3. **Reddy, K. (2013)** analyses the Ambedkar led Dalit movement with an anthropological perspective. He observes that mission of Ambedkar was aimed at bringing about radical

transformation in the living conditions of millions of his community who had been condemned for many centuries to live degraded and dehumanized lives.

4. **Sudhi Mandloi (2015)** in her study 'Dr Ambedkar's Philosophy on Democracy and his Dissent: An Analytical Study of Ambedkar's Socio- Political Ideas' she remarked that Dr. Ambedkar was one of the greatest architects of modern India. His contribution to the progression socio-political and constitutional thought has been quite noteworthy. He has been regarded as Father of the Indian constitution'. He was a nationalist, democrat and principally a humanist. Throughout his life, he fought for the rights of subjugated section of the society. He had a vision of an uncensored society based on the belief of 'liberty, equality and fraternity'. He dream of an egalitarian society remained disgruntled even today in the twenty first century. Indian society is still being crippled by caste system, inequality, religious prejudices and social injustice which in turn obstructing the path of Indian Democracy.
5. **Prasanna K. (2016)** argues that the hypothetical base of Social justice promises an individual to guard against any oppression discrimination and deprivation of social, Economic and political liberty. Its social sphere argues for equality in terms of expression of ideas, belief, faith, and worship etc.it also facilitates the opportunity to promote the dignity of individual and respectful life. Social justice in terms of economic activities provide an equal opportunity for participation in Economic activities to all without any discrimination and believe on the equal distribution of income and wealth, accessibility to basic necessities to all, provision of housing health and sanitation facilities as well as other social safety nets. In its political perspective of all citizens in political affairs, no one should deny from participation in political activities on the basis of caste, clan, gender, race etc.

SIGNIFICATION OF THE STUDY:

India's economic growth rate is running very fast most of the macro indicators look positive. Dr Ambedkar has expressed his views on public finance, rate of interest, problems of rupees land reform mode of farming and industrialization on deferent occasions the underlying motive of all his thinking was to lift the untouchable classes who were predominantly landless or small peasant cultivators his views toughly denoted his progressive nature. Since the beginning of NEP 1991 Government of India continuously reduces its share from the public sector industries

However data shows that is not happening. On the country government expenditure on social and economic over head is grossly inadequate to the needs. Therefore, it creates income and wealth inequality, unethical activities, demoralizing the youth, violation etc. This is not surely not good for long term smooth economic development of any country. His economic study maintains that balance in both sectors public and private systematically. He suggested nationalization of life insurance and advocated state management and state ownership in industry for benefit of the poor and down trodden classes. To him men different from each other due to their birth method. To promote rapid economic development through creation and expansion of Infrastructure, to promote financial resources, to promote small scale industries etc. So the research focuses on golden path of development in this study. Therefore Ambedkar economic development is need to Indian economic development for betterment of India.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Dr. Ambedkar became one of the first out caste to obtain a college education in India eventually earning law degree and doctorates for his study and research in Law economic and political Science from Columbia University and the London School of economics. One who make economic model and policies of Ambedkar principles are very essential to input the policy formation his thought of economic mainly focused on the problem of rupees land reform, gold standards, public finance, land holding and monetary policies effect of rate of interest on bank and industries more important factor in the development of economic study information of the economic policies. Dr. Ambedkar contribution as an economist unfortunate this lack of awareness to an extent could be explained by his phenomenal contribution in the other spheres such as law religion and economics might have over shadowed his contribution to Indian economics.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

1. To study the economic thoughts of Dr. Ambedkar for Indian economy and relevance of these thoughts in current scenario.
2. . To study the Economic thoughts of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar
3. To study the relevance of Agriculture thoughts of Bharat Ratan Dr. B. R. Ambedkar.

4. To know the Relevance of Dr. Ambedkar's study on development Indian economy.
5. To study the view on Labour movement and its relevance to present labour market.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The present research paper is based on secondary data. Various reference, journals and books have been used for the research paper.

- **Sources of Data**

The research study is based on both descriptive and analytical method. The study is based on secondary data.

Secondary data will be collected from various books, journals, internet, information, magazines. News papers, ph.D and M.phil thesis are referred.

CHAPTER SCHEME:

The present study is organized into six

Chapters as follows:

CHAPTER-1: Research Design

The chapter will reveal regarding, Introduction of the study, Statement of the problem, significance of the study, Objective of the study, research methodology, Chapter Scheme, Limitations of the study.

CHAPTER-2: Review of Literature

CHAPTER-3: Life sketch of Dr. Ambedkar.

CHAPTER-4: Relevance of economic thoughts of Dr. B. R. Ambedkar in India.

CHAPTER-5: Dr. Ambedkar View and its Relevance in present India.

CHAPTER-6: Findings, Suggestion and Conclusion.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

The present study has the following limitations.

1. The present study is only about on development of Indian economy of Dr B. R. Ambedkar.
2. The present research work highlights only Ambedkar and its relevance for Indian economy.

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